

EXPLORING THE EFFICACY OF DRIED WHITE MULBERRY FRUIT IN MODULATING LIPID PROFILES AND URIC ACID LEVELS IN WISTAR RAT MODEL

MANAL ABD-ELSALAM KANOUEA

Pharmaceutical Sciences Program, Faculty of Pharmacy, Applied Science Private University, Amman-Jordan. Email: manalkanouaa@gmail.com

MARAM ALTAH

Al-Qadisiyeh College, School of Pharmacy, Amman-Jordan. Email: maram_altah@yahoo.com

REEM FAWAZ ABUTAYEH *

Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry and Pharmacognosy, Faculty of Pharmacy, Applied Science Private University, Amman-Jordan. *Corresponding Authors Email: r_abutayeh@asu.edu.jo

SHATHA ALSHAER

Clinical Pharmacy and Therapeutics Department, Applied Science Private University, Amman, Jordan. Email: shathamalshaer@yahoo.com

Abstract

Objective: Originating from traditional Chinese medicine (TCM), and Ayurveda practices in managing hyperlipidemia and diabetes mellitus, the use of commercial dried white mulberry (*Morus alba*) fruit is prevalent today. To this end, this study investigated the modulatory effect of dried white mulberry fruit aqueous extract (WMF-AE) on the serum lipid profiles and uric acid levels in rat models. **Materials and methods:** The acute hyperuricemia model was induced in rats using potassium oxonate (250 mg/kg), and the dyslipidemia model was induced using a high-fat diet (10% lamb fat and 1.5% cholesterol mixed with 88.5% of regular rats' chow). Dried WMF-AE were orally administered to both models using 5 and 10 mg/kg doses respectively. Serum uric acid (UA), total cholesterol (TC), triglycerides (TG), high-density lipoprotein-cholesterol (HDL-C), and low-density lipoprotein-cholesterol (LDL-C) levels were determined. Rats were then sacrificed for histopathological examination of their livers. **Results:** The dried WMF-AE significantly reduced body weight for rats served either with a normal or a high-fat diet. The WMF-AE significantly reduced serum uric acid in acute hyperuricemia male rats when compared to rats with no treatment. Moreover, it significantly decreased serum LDL-C in certain studied groups and effectively protected the liver tissues from fatty changes that may appear due to a fatty diet. **Conclusion:** Dried WMF-AE exhibit positive effects in managing weight, reducing serum uric acid, and LDL-C levels when applied to acute hyperuricemia rat models fed on high-fat diets.

Keywords: White Mulberry Fruit, Anti-hyperuricemic, Anti-hyperlipidemic, Wistar Rat.

1. INTRODUCTION

Dyslipidemia frequently co-occurs with hyperuricemia, where 25% to 60% of gout patients experience hypertriglyceridemia. In addition, this co-occurrence is reportedly linked to an increased incidence of coronary artery diseases (CAD) in some patients, suggesting that UA concentration might be an indicator of coronary risk, including the risk for myocardial infarction, which is the most common acute manifestation of CAD (Amanolahi and Rakhshande, 2013; Singh and Cleveland, 2018). Hyperuricemia can also be considered a bioindicator for other metabolic syndromes such as hypertension and hyperinsulinemia. Factors like obesity, alcohol consumption, and genetic predispositions are strongly associated with the clinical co-occurrence of dyslipidemia and hyperuricemia (Tian et al., 2020).

Gout is defined as inflammatory arthritis caused by hyperuricemia and the accumulation of monosodium UA crystals in the joints (Aung et al., 2017). Elevated serum UA levels i.e. hyperuricemia is clinically known as gout. Gout varies from episodes of disabling acute arthritis (flares), chronic recurrent arthritis, persistent low-grade joint inflammation, and potentially progressive disease joint damage (Gliozzi et al., 2015). Management of gout is centered upon lowering the UA levels below the threshold for crystal formation with UA-lowering therapy (ULT). However, patients treated with ULT were reported to be non-adherent (Aung et al., 2017).

Poor adherence to ULT has been mainly explained by the side effects accompanying its use, especially during the first 6 months of the treatment regimen. Where decreases in serum UA would cause transient localized reabsorption and precipitation of monosodium UA crystals in the cartilage and soft tissues, resulting in an increased frequency of gout flares experienced by patients. In addition, patients fear the adverse effects of long-term use of UTL and their interactions with other drugs (Aung et al., 2017). Hyperlipidemia is the most common type of dyslipidemia and is considered a risk factor for cardiovascular diseases (CVD) (Alloubani et al., 2020). Management of hyperlipidemia includes highly effective lipid-lowering medications, such as the 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl-coenzyme A (HMG-CoA) reductase inhibitors (also known as statins) (Mormone et al., 2024; Venkateshan et al., 2016).

However, many patients do not achieve the lipid profile goal levels recommended by guidelines. Failures in goal achievement have been attributed to a variety of causes, however the most important is poor adherence to treatment, in the form of irregular or interrupted intake and high frequency of discontinuation or lack of persistence (Tragni and Catapano, 2012). In the case of statins, poor adherence is mainly elucidated by its side effects, in particular statin-associated muscle symptoms (SAMS), which include: myopathy, myalgia, myositis, and rhabdomyolysis (Thompson et al., 2016). In addition, hyperlipidemia is an asymptomatic condition that makes patients take medication lightly, except in cases where patients have sufficient perception of the future risks of non-adherence (Tragni and Catapano 2012; Thompson et al. 2016).

When pursuing complementary and/or alternative therapies, traditional herbal medicine, including Ayurvedic medicine and Traditional Chinese medicine (TCM), is appealing. Where they are now being investigated for bioactivities against miscellaneous diseases including hyperlipidemia and hyperuricemia. In addition, traditional herbal medicine provides a source of treatment with fewer side effects, less drug-drug interaction, and at the same time patients tend to adhere better to traditional forms of treatment and supplements (Aloke et al., 2021; Nguyen et al., 2016).

White mulberry (*Morus alba*) is cultivated in many countries including China, India, Japan, North Africa, and Arabia (Memete et al., 2022). It is a multi-functional tree, where the leaves of the plant exhibit strong antimicrobial and antidiabetic activities (Oliveira et al., 2015). The twigs were reported to contain Mulberroside A, which was reported to have potent uricosuric and neuroprotective effects in hyperuricemic rats (Wang et al., 2011). *Morus alba* The root bark has shown antidiabetic activity enhanced by insulin sensitization (Wang et al., 2011; Ha et al., 2018).

In addition, the fruit has demonstrated the ability to prevent hyperlipidemia, manage lipid profile in a hyperlipidemic rat model, and scavenge free radicals (Yang et al., 2010; Zafar et al., 2013). However, up till today, the action of the fruit of *Morus alba* against hyperlipidemia and hyperuricemia has not been thoroughly studied yet. Healthcare systems and healthcare professionals need to address the management of patients with several coexisting diseases who are now the norm rather than the exception. This study aimed to explore and evaluate the efficacy of commercially available dried WMF-AE in improving lipid profiles and uric acid serum levels when both diseases are found simultaneously, besides evaluating its activity on both diseases when found separately.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was performed following the regulations of good laboratory practices (GLP), and all of the experimental protocols were approved by the Applied Science Private University Ethics Committee for the Care and Use of Experimental Animals in Education and Scientific Research – Faculty of Pharmacy (Approval number: 2020- PHA- 2)

2.1. Extraction procedure

Commercial Organic Sun-dried WMF-AE was bought from Amazon (origin: Turkey). Three hundred and fifty grams of the fruit was weighed and soaked in 800 ml of warm distilled water to soften the fruit. Then the mixture was blended with an electric blender and heated for half an hour in a water bath at 37°C. The fruit was filtered with filter paper (#41) to get rid of the extra water and fructose. The solid residues were mixed after filtration to form a slurry of nearly 800 ml in total which was enough for 3 days. The animals were given the slurry by oral gavage once daily.

2.2. In vivo Study

The method of this study was adopted from (Yang and colleagues) and (Kim and colleagues) (Yang et al., 2010; Kim et al., 2017) methodology with some modifications. Five-week-old Wistar rats were used in this study, with an average body weight of 173.3 g (115 -230 g) for male rats and an average body weight of 153.3 g (115-185 g) for female rats. They were kept in controlled rooms at 25°C and 55% humidity with 24-hour light-dark cycles and continuous air circulation. Rats were put separately in cages with wooden shaving and fed a commercially normal diet (Local Supplier, Jordan) and freshwater was always offered. After 1 week of adaptation, 53 rats (29 males and 24 females) were randomly divided into 8 groups (Table 1).

Table 1: In-vivo, the experiment groups, and the treatments that were used

Groups Numbers	Status	Classification	Diet	Treatments	Total number of rats	Number of Males	Number of Females
Group I	Healthy	Control group	Commercial normal diet	Without Treatment	6	3	3
Group II	Hyperuricemic	Test Group	Commercial normal diet	5 g/kg of the dried WMF-AE	7	4	3
Group III	Hyperuricemic	Test Group	Commercial normal diet	10 g/kg the dried WMF-AE	7	4	3
Group IV	Hyperlipidemic + Hyperuricemic	Positive Control Group	High-fat diet	4 mg/kg Simvastatin + 10 mg/kg Allopurinol	6	3	3
Group V	Hyperlipidemic + Hyperuricemic	Negative Control Group	High-fat diet	Without Treatment	7	4	3
Group VI	Hyperlipidemic + Hyperuricemic	Test Group	High-fat diet	5 g/kg of the dried WMF-AE	7	4	3
Group VII	Hyperlipidemic + Hyperuricemic	Test Group	High-fat diet	10 g/kg of the dried WMF-AE	7	4	3
Group VIII	Hyperlipidemic	Test Group	High-fat diet	5 g/kg of the dried WMF-AE + 4 mg/kg Simvastatin + 10 mg/kg Allopurinol	6	3	3

2.3. Hyperlipidemia and Hyperuricemia Model

Hyperlipidemia was induced in groups IV- VIII by feeding them a high-fat diet containing (10% lamb fat, 1.5% cholesterol, and 88.5% commercial normal diet) for four weeks. The high-fat diet was prepared by melting lamb fat under 121°C and mixing it with normal commercial feed and cholesterol powder. After four weeks, the acute hyperuricemia model was induced in all groups, except groups I and VIII by administering potassium oxonate, a selectively competitive urease inhibitor, at a single dose of 250 mg/kg intraperitoneally (Tang et al., 2017). All rats were treated with the dried WMF-AE in all groups except the control groups I, IV, and V. Groups IV, and VIII were treated with 10 mg/kg allopurinol orally once daily post-hyperuricemia induction. Groups IV and VIII were treated with 4 mg/kg Simvastatin to compare the efficacy of the WMF-AE relative to that of the conventional medicine. All treatments were given to the rats in the morning after an overnight fasting status (Table 1).

2.4. Serum Biochemistry analysis in rats:

Blood samples of rats were drawn from the retro-orbital venous sinus at overnight fasting status, at two points of time: in the first week (Day Zero) before inducing the hyperlipidemia model (before giving the high-fat diet) and at the end of the four weeks study duration (Day 28), before animal scarification. Serum were obtained by centrifuging the blood samples at 5000 RMP for 5 min. Serum biochemistry parameters including lipid profile (TC, TAG, HDL-C, LDL-C) and UA levels were determined by using ultraviolet enzymatic kits (Biosystem, Spain), (Spinreact, Spain), (Bioresearch, Jordan), (Biosystem, Spain), and (Biosystem, Jordan) respectively.

2.5. Assessment of rats' weekly weights and liver weights:

Rats' weights were measured weekly to check for weight changes among different groups, using a digital scale (BEL Engineering, Italy).

2.6. Histological examination of liver sections:

The rat liver specimens were put in the Auto processor machine (Thermo Fisher, USA) overnight, where they were gradually fixed in 10% formalin, dehydrated by alcohol, and cleared by xylene. Specimens were then embedded in liquid paraffin manually to prepare paraffin blocks by using a Tissue embedding system (Maxtech, Pakistan) and cold plate (Diapath, Italy). After that trimming and Sectioning of the paraffinized blocks were done at 10 and 5 µm thicknesses respectively by using a microtome (Leica, Germany). The sections were fixed by albumin in a glass slide and dried in a dry air oven (Lipshaw, US) till they were deparaffinized. Standard hematoxylin and eosin (H and E) stain procedures were used to stain all the sections. A light microscope equipped with a computer-controlled digital camera was used to visualize images on the slides (Walker and Gautier, 2011). A pathologist examined the liver specimens and reported the results (Dr. Heba Kalbouneh, Jordan University).

2.7. Statistical Analysis

Analysis was performed between all the groups using the parameters obtained within the duration of the study. Parameters entered in the analysis included initial body weight, final body weight, weight gain, liver weights, lipid profile, and UA analysis parameters. Data are presented using mean ± SD (Standard Deviation of Mean). The statistical analyses were determined by using IBM SPSS version 21 (Statistical Package for the Social Science, Chicago, Illinois). This included One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) using Dunnett's post-hoc test, independent sample T-test, and Paired Sample T-test for parameters showing normality using Kolmogorov-Smirnov^a test. While Kruskal-Wallis, Mann-Whitney

U, and Wilcoxon Signed Rank tests were used for the parameters that failed to show the normality of the initial parameter. A p -value < 0.05 was considered significant.

3. RESULTS

3.1. The effect of the dried WMF-AE on rat weights

The ANOVA tool with Dunnett's post-hoc analysis was used to compare the mean weights of different groups against the mean weights of the control groups (I, V, and VI).

Regarding males' rats

At baseline (Day-Zero) the control groups showed no significant difference in between their mean weights, and the treatment groups showed no significant difference in their mean weights compared to the mean weights of all control groups.

Although the final mean weights for groups (I, II, III, VII, and VIII) only showed a significant difference when compared to Group V (p -values 0.007, 0.036, 0.000, 0.002, and 0.000 respectively), the weight gained for Group III showed the lowest compared to the groups (Figure 1/ Panel A).

Regarding females' rats

As for male's mean weights at Day-Zero, the mean weights for the control groups showed no significant difference in their mean weights, and the treatment groups showed no significant difference in their mean weights compared to the three control groups.

The final mean weights for the treatment groups and the control groups did not show any significant differences from the final mean weights for group I. Despite this, the average weight of group III showed the lowest weight gained (Figure 1/ Panel B).

Figure 1: Panel A shows the effect of White mulberry fruit therapy on the mean body weights of Male rats in grams. Panel B shows the effect of the dried WMF-AE therapy on the mean body weights of Female rats in grams. (Data are expressed as means (±SD), ^a $p < 0.05$ vs. Group I, and ^b $p < 0.05$ vs. Group V)

3.2. Effect of the dried WMF-AE on UA levels in rats

Comparing mean UA levels between males and females at the initial and final readings showed no significant differences (p -values=0.361, 0.192 respectively). The final mean of UA readings for each treatment group was compared to the final mean of the control groups.

Regarding males' rats

The groups (I and V) were both used as negative controls to check the levels that serum UA would reach upon induction of hyperuricemia and if there was any difference between UA levels in different feed patterns. The mean difference between Group I and Group V in male rats was 0.58 mg/dl with no significant difference (p -value= 0.1) in the final mean UA level. The treatment groups showed final mean UA serum UA levels lower than that of Group V with mean UA differences of 1.19, 1.25, 0.91, 1.57, and 0.77 mg/dl for groups (II, III, VI, VII, and VIII) respectively. Group IV was the main control group that the treatment groups were compared to, to check for the efficacy of the dried WMF-AE against acute hyperuricemia. Although all groups have a higher mean UA level in males compared to Group IV, yet three treatment groups (I, V, and VIII) were not significantly different from Group IV (Figure 2).

Regarding females' rats

The female in group I had the highest mean serum UA levels and just like the males the female in group IV readings were the lowest. The mean difference between the females in groups (I and IV) was 1.84 mg/dl (p -value= 0.0). Unlike the male readings, the female in Group V readings was closest to the Group IV levels with a mean difference of 0.79 mg/dl, and no significant difference was found between them (p -value=0.13). Comparing the final mean serum UA levels for the treatment groups in females with Group IV, mean differences were 1.28, 1.83, 0.82, 1.68 mg/dl, and 1.74 for groups (II, III, VI, VII, and VIII) respectively (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Males show the effect of the dried WMF-AE therapy on the mean Uric acid levels of Male rats in mg/dL. Females show the effect of the dried WMF-AE therapy on the mean Uric acid levels of female rats in mg/dL. (Data are expressed as means, ^a $p < 0.05$ vs. Group I, and ^b $p < 0.05$ vs. Group IV)

3.3. Effect of the dried WMF-AE on TC levels in rats

A comparison of the initial and final mean TC serum levels among groups (both males and females) is shown in (Figure 3). Although there was no significant difference in the means of treatment groups and those of the controls, in both male and female rats, the highest increase in levels was seen in Group VIII, and the smallest increase was seen in Group VI. Yet it is noted that Group VIII has

distinguishable mean differences from its corresponding control groups in both males and females. Moreover, statistical differences were spotted in females in Group VIII compared with groups (I and IV) (mean difference: 46.8 and 42.67, p -value=0.03 and 0.04 respectively), but this group showed no significant difference from Group V.

Figure 3: Male shows the effect of the dried WMF-AE therapy on the mean Total Cholesterol levels of Male rats in mg/dL. Female shows the effect of the dried WMF-AE therapy on the mean Total Cholesterol levels of female rats in mg/dL

3.4. Effect of the dried WMF-AE on TG levels in rats

A comparison of the initial and final mean TG serum levels among groups (both males and females) is shown in (Figure 4). The highest increase in levels was seen in Group V, and the main decrease was seen in Group III.

Figure 4: Male shows the effect of the dried WMF-AE therapy on the mean Triglyceride levels of Male rats in mg/dL. Female shows the effect of the dried WMF-AE therapy on the mean Triglyceride levels of female rats in mg/dL

Results were classified according to gender. Results showed that there was no significant difference in the means of treatment groups and those of the controls, in male rats, nor were there any mean differences among different groups. The final readings in TG female serum levels for most of the treatment groups were found to have lower levels than Group I with significant differences for groups

(II, III, and VIII) (p -value= 0.05). Group VI levels were lower than the Group I but were not significantly different. Group VII and the control groups (IV and V) had a higher level in final TG but there was no significant difference to the Group I level. Comparing the final TG means between males and females in their respective control groups showed that the effect of a high-fat diet was more pronounced in females as opposed to its effect in males.

3.5. Effect of the dried WMF-AE on HDL-C levels in rats

A comparison of the initial and final mean HDL-C serum levels among groups (both males and females) is shown in (Table 2). A pattern of HDL-C decrease is seen in both male and female control groups (I and IV). While the final HDL-C levels were comparable in Group IV, the HDL-C final levels were increased in all treatment groups.

Table 2: Density lipoprotein levels of control and treatment groups at Day-Zero and Day-28

Groups		I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII
Initial (Day-Zero)	Male	47.04±8.39	12.72±8.8	19.6±3.26	38.4±7.96	17.92±16.22	2.4±9.78	12.72±13.3	19.6±9.78
	Female	45.23±4.81	17.49±9.92	9.28±2.06	54.6±12.22	4.16±34.01	54.61±2.73	17.49±8.0	9.28±5.33
Final (Day-28)	Male	30.9±1.4	15.1±14.5	21.1±11.3	25.8±1.4	25.8±1.4	15.12±1.3	17.68±0.3	33.5±5.7
	Female	30.5±1.5	20.0±14	40±4.7	33.8±14.8	20.05±14.8	35.2±5.8	22.08±13.33	39.0±6.1

Results showed that there was no significant difference in the means of treatment groups and those of the controls, in male rats, nor were there any mean differences among different groups. When comparing HDL-C serum levels for male groups, groups (VIII and II) showed a significant increase in the HDL-C readings compared to Group V (p -value = 0.032 and 0.034 respectively). Moreover, groups (VIII II, and III) showed a significant increase in the HDL-C readings compared to Group IV (p -value= 0.032, 0.034, and 0.034 respectively). There were no significant differences in the final HDL-C levels between treatment groups. As for female groups, Group VII detected significant differences when compared to groups (I and V) (p -value=0.046 and 0.05 respectively), and the Group III level was significantly different than Group V (p -value=0.046).

3.6. Effect of the dried WMF-AE on LDL-C levels in rats

A comparison of the initial and final mean LDL-C serum levels among groups (both males and females) is shown in (Table 3). Results showed that there was no significant difference in the means of treatment groups and those of the controls', in male rats. As for the female treatment groups, groups (VIII and III) increase in levels were significant in comparison to Group V (p -values= 0.016 and 0049 respectively). It is worth noting that Group VI in both genders showed a decrease in final mean LDL levels, although differences were not statistically significant.

Table 3: Low Density lipoprotein levels of control and treatment groups at Day-Zero and Day-28

		I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII
Initial (Day-Zero)	Male	45.18±19.67	13.28±7.0	8.88±5.11	40.43±18.16	41.83±4.14	55.72±24.12	50.155±13.78	13.29±7.93
	Female	29.92±4.81	7.59±9.92	3.81±2.06	40.64±25.37	50.04±34.01	44.64±2.73	42.45±9.92	3.81±5.33
Final (Day-28)	Male	38.8±9.6	35.39±14	30.51±8.4	47.8±12.3	54.1±12.3	40.32±12	53.26±13.8	74.4±32.7
	Female	30.9±3	17.48±12.1	66.41±11.2	29.3±20.7	21.17±13.7	40.65±14	39.8±22.8	74.8±23.9

3.7. Histological examination of liver sections

Histological investigation of rats' liver specimens was applied to different treatment groups, to examine the presence of hepatic steatosis or any hepatocyte damage. Results are shown in (Figure 5). The specimens demonstrated clear and normal hepatocyte histology except in Group V, in which the adipose tissue vacuoles were detected, indicating a potential of developing hepatic steatosis. The specimens were checked and diagnosed by a pathologist.

	Group II	Group II	Group III	Group IV
Liver Section Specimens				
Comments	Normal histology	Normal histology	Normal histology	Normal histology
	Group V	Group VI	Group VII	Group VIII
Liver Section Specimens				
Comments	- Slight fatty change - Presence of adipose vascular degeneration	Normal histology	Normal histology	Normal histology

Figure 5: Hematoxylin/eosin staining of liver specimens for rats on Day 28 of different treatments

4. DISCUSSION

In the present study, we evaluated the potential effect of sun-dried mulberry fruit products on weight gain, lipid profile, and uric acid levels in hyperlipidemic and acute hyperuricemia models using male and female Wister rats. The effect was studied for its potential when given as a chief component and when given in combination with conventional drugs (simvastatin).

In this study, as shown in (Figure 1) the pattern of weight change differs between males and females when calculated about the final baseline created by calculating the final mean of Group I. In the male rat model, the effect of the high-fat diet was observed, where Group V for the high-fat diet had the highest weight increase in the male rat model. Moreover, the groups that were given high fat diet had a higher weight gain than those taking a normal diet, except for the group taking combined treatment with simvastatin (Group VIII) in both genders which was given the high-fat diet in addition to the mulberry fruit and the lipid-lowering drug simvastatin. These observations indicate that the mulberry fruit has a potential for weight-control activity in cases of taking the normal diet, but it does not have this effect in high-fat diets. Also, it indicates a potential for having a synergistic effect when given with simvastatin even in high-fat diet-fed female rats.

This pattern was not observed in males, but when considering the amount of gain within each group individually, the groups (III and VIII) had the lowest gain in weight in both male and female models and the high-fat diet-fed groups had a higher gain than the one in Group I in both male and female. Both patterns of weight gain results identify the prophylactic effect of the mulberry fruit against weight gain and even having a weight-reducing effect when given with a normal diet. The results are different from those found in a recent study that reported that the mulberry fruit did not affect weight gain in both normal and high-fat diets in Wistar rats (Yang et al., 2010). The differences in the observed results between the two studies are justified by the difference in the method of administration of the fruit between the two studies, where in this study we introduced the full dose of treatment by oral gavage while in the previous study; they supplemented the dose within the feed of the rats.

Regarding UA levels (Figure 2), these results have shown a difference related to the gender of rats. In males, the effect of high-dose mulberry fruit seems to have an effect that is not statistically different from that of the group IV treated with allopurinol. The female rats' results indicate a potential for hyperuricemia alleviation in Group VI which means in high-fat diet cases at a dose of 5 g, only. This difference can be explained by the female hormonal changes during the catamenial cycle. UA levels are highest during the follicular phase and decline during the luteal phase (Mumford et al., 2013). Since this is the first research that studied the effect of white mulberry fruit on acute hyperuricemia, we attribute that potential to the presence of flavonoids (0.39%) (Yang et al., 2010), which showed an ability to decrease serum uric acid in urolithiasis rats (Chavada K et al., 2012), and to the resveratrol (0.03%) (Yang et al., 2010), that had a uricosuric and nephroprotective activity by regulating renal organic ion transporters in hyperuricemic mice (Shi et al., 2012).

Regarding TC, the only group that showed a notable increase in TC levels was group VIII in both male and female models, and it even showed a statistically significant increase in the female rat models when compared to the control groups (Figure 3). Group VII showed the lowest TC level among all-male groups and had a lower triglyceride level compared to Group IV. In females, the lowest TC levels were found in Group II. This observation agrees with reported results in previous animal studies (Yang et al., 2010) as well as in a human study that included 58 hypercholesterolemic adults aged between 30–60 years old, who were given 45 g freeze-dried mulberry fruit for 6 weeks (Zhang and Ma, n.d., 2018; Sirikancharod et al., 2016). The differences in final readings of TC levels among males and females can be described by changing the lipoprotein cholesterol levels during the menstrual cycle in response to changes in reproductive hormone levels (Mumford et al., 2017).

The TG serum levels did not show any significant difference either in male or female rats when compared to their respective controls. Although there was a slight decrease in the TG serum levels in groups served with a normal diet and mulberry fruit, where the 5 g white mulberry had the best-decreasing activity among normal diet in female groups (Figure 4). Although in this study 5 g had a slight lowering effect on the TG levels, which is similar to the findings of a previous experimental study (Yang et al., 2010).

The high-fat diet groups that were served with 5g/Kg of white mulberry fruit showed another interesting effect on TG levels in which this concentration had a better-lowering effect on TG levels than Group V. Further, this result agrees with a previous experimental study that was done on rabbits fed with a high-cholesterol diet plus mulberry fruit that showed a higher decrement in rabbit's TG and LDL-C serum levels compared to rabbits fed with high high-cholesterol alone. The effect on TG serum levels is because of the presence of 24.3% dietary fiber, which is well known to decrease TAG levels through inhibition of hepatic lipogenesis, and lower plasma LDL-C concentration via blocking cholesterol and bile acid absorption and increasing LDL-C-receptor activity (Venkatesan et al., 2003). In current study, there was no significant difference in HDL-C male and female serum levels. An increase in HDL-C levels was detected in all of the treatment groups, while a decrease was seen in the

control groups. The decreased HDL-C levels in the control groups and the increased levels in the treatment groups give a positive indication of the effect of white mulberry fruit on HDL-C levels. Although the lowest final HDL-C levels were detected in groups (II and VII), that was because their initial levels were very low (Table 2).

Our results are semi-harmonious with a previous study (Yang et al., 2010). We can attribute the increase in HDL-C levels and the decrease in LDL-C levels to the presence of anthocyanin (0.087%) and flavonoid (0.39%) found in the mulberry fruit (Devi and Augusti, 2003; Vinson et al., 1998). A study done in 2008 reported that after 12 weeks of administration of anthocyanin capsules (80mg), the serum LDL-C concentration of people aged 40–65 years diagnosed with dyslipidemia showed a significant decrease in their LDL-C level by 13.63%, and a significant increase in their serum HDL-C concentration by 12.42%, with no change for serum TC and TG levels (Yang et al., 2010). Another study done on flavonoids resulted in an inhibition of the oxidative modification of LDL-C by macrophages, also the study approved that consuming flavonoids in the normal human diet may raise the possibility of protection against atherosclerosis (Whalley et al., 1990).

Among all the groups tested, Group VIII showed a sharp increase in the level of TC and LDL-C when compared to other groups, and we can explain this by the interaction between simvastatin and white mulberry fruit which is based on a pharmacokinetic interaction. Simvastatin is metabolized by the isoenzyme cytochrome P450 3A4 (CYP3A4) (Ward et al., 2019), and when co-administered with a CYP3A4 inhibitors drug, such as azole antifungals and amiodarone, its concentrations increase in the plasma and may cause myopathy and/or rhabdomyolysis (Ward et al., 2019). On the other hand, if it was co-administered with CYP3A4 inducer, it would have decreased plasma levels and would not work efficiently. In general, most berry families including white mulberry are rich in phenolics, anthocyanins, flavonoids, and mulberries that have been proven to be P-glycoprotein and CYP4503A4 modulators *in vivo* (Hsu et al., 2013).

Consequently, the CYP4503A4 induction ability of mulberry fruit might be the reason for the decreased efficacy of simvastatin (Hsu et al., 2013). -Furthermore, in the current attempt to augment the antihyperlipidemic activity of mulberry fruit, the histopathological examination was done of liver sections derived from the tested rats; the entire group's sections showed clear and normal histology except for the group served with a high-fat diet alone with no treatment (Group V). The liver sections of Group V showed adipose vacuoles inside the hepatocyte. Since this is the first study to investigate the efficacy of white mulberry fruit on hepatocyte protection from hyperlipidemia rat model, the current results can be deduced that the consumption of white mulberry has a hepatoprotective activity against fatty liver change and can prevent the formation of adipose vacuoles.

5. CONCLUSION

Taking White mulberry fruit daily for hyperlipidemic or hyperuricemic patients or even for people who aim to lose weight, is a promising strategy to target hyperlipidemia, hyperuricemia, and weight gain. This fruit can decrease LDL-C, increase HDL-C, decrease TAG, decrease UA serum levels and weight control, and has hepatoprotective activity in hyperlipidemic rats. Thereby it can be used efficiently for these diseases. However, the combination of simvastatin and white mulberry does not show any improvement in lipid profile due to certain pharmacokinetic interactions. This great fruit deserves further testing to investigate its other activities and enhance its antihyperlipidemic and anti-hyperuricemic activity, especially for chronic hyperuricemia.

Competing Interests

All authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- 1) Alloubani A, Nimer R, Samara R. 2020. Relationship between Hyperlipidemia, Cardiovascular Disease and Stroke: A Systematic Review. *Current Cardiology Reviews*, 17(6).
<https://doi.org/10.2174/1573403x16999201210200342>
- 2) Alope C, Nwachukwu N, Obasi N A, Emelike C U, Amu P A, Ogbu P N, Ogbonnia E C. 2021. Antihyperglycemic, antihyperlipidemic and hepatoprotective effects of *Ficus ottoniifolia* (Miq.) Miq. supplementation in alloxan-induced diabetic rats. *Avicenna Journal of Phytomedicine*, 11(5): 428–435.
<https://doi.org/10.22038/AJP.2020.16958>
- 3) Amanolahi F, Rakhshande H. 2013. Effects of ethanolic extract of green tea on decreasing the level of lipid profile in rat. *Avicenna Journal of Phytomedicine*, 3(1): 98–105.
<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/25050263>
<http://www.pubmedcentral.nih.gov/articlerender.fcgi?artid=PMC4075689>
- 4) Aung T, Myung G, FitzGerald J D. 2017. Treatment approaches and adherence to urate-lowering therapy for patients with gout. *Patient Preference and Adherence*, 11: 795–800.
<https://doi.org/10.2147/PPA.S97927>
- 5) Contribution O. 2003. Increased binding of LDL and VLDL to apo B, E receptors of hepatic plasma membrane of rats treated with Fibernat, 271: 262–271. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00394-003-0420-8>
- 6) Devi K S, Augusti K T. 2003. Mechanism of action of anti atherogenic and related effects of *Ficus bengalensis* Linn. flavonoids in experimental animals, 41(4): 296–303.
- 7) Fitzgerald J D. 2017. Treatment approaches and adherence to urate-lowering therapy for patients with gout, 795–800.
- 8) Gliozzi M, Malara N, Muscoli S, Mollace V. 2015. The treatment of hyperuricemia. *International Journal of Cardiology*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijcard.2015.08.087>
- 9) Glycoprotein P, Cytochrome P, Hsu P, Shia C, Lin S, Chao P L, Juang S. 2013. Potential Risk of Mulberry Drug Interaction : Modulation on.
- 10) Ha M T, Seong S H, Nguyen T D, Cho W K, Ah K J, Ma J Y, Min B S. 2018. Chalcone derivatives from the root bark of *Morus alba* L. act as inhibitors of PTP1B and α -glucosidase. *Phytochemistry*, 155(7): 114–125.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phytochem.2018.08.001>
- 11) Kim J K, Kim W J, Hyun J M, Lee J S, Kwon J G, Seo C, Choi Y. 2017. *Salvia plebeia* Extract Inhibits Xanthine Oxidase Activity in Vitro and Reduces Serum Uric Acid in an Animal Model of Hyperuricemia. *Planta Medica*, 83(17): 1335–1341. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0043-111012>
- 12) Memete A R, Timar A V, Vuscan A N, Miere F, Venter A C, Vicas S I. 2022. Phytochemical Composition of Different Botanical Parts of *Morus* Species, Health Benefits and Application in Food Industry. *Plants*, 11(2).
<https://doi.org/10.3390/plants11020152>
- 13) Mormone A, Tortorella G, Esposito F, Caturano A, Marrone A, Cozzolino D, Rinaldi L. 2024. Advances in Pharmacological Approaches for Managing Hypercholesterolemia : A Comprehensive Overview of Novel Treatments.
- 14) Mumford S L, Dasharathy S, Pollack A Z. 2017. Variations in lipid levels according to menstrual cycle phase : clinical implications Variations in lipid levels according to menstrual cycle phase : clinical implications, 4299.
- 15) Mumford S L, Dasharathy S S, Pollack A Z, Perkins N J, Mattison D R, Cole S R, Schisterman E F. 2013. Serum uric acid in relation to endogenous reproductive hormones during the menstrual cycle : findings from the BioCycle study, 28(7): 1853–1862. <https://doi.org/10.1093/humrep/det085>
- 16) Nguyen G C, Croitoru K, Silverberg M S, Steinhart A H, Weizman A V. 2016. Use of Complementary and Alternative Medicine for Inflammatory Bowel Disease Is Associated with Worse Adherence to Conventional Therapy : The COMPLIANT Study, 22(6): 1412–1417. <https://doi.org/10.1097/MIB.0000000000000773>

- 17) Oliveira A M De, Mesquita S, Cavalcante G, Lima E D O, Medeiros, P L De, Maria P, Napoleão T H. 2015. Evaluation of Toxicity and Antimicrobial Activity of an Ethanolic Extract from Leaves of *Morus alba* L. (Moraceae). *Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*.
- 18) Publication A. 2017. Pharmacology Potassium oxonate induces acute hyperuricemia in the tree shrew (*Tupaia belangeri chinensis*).
- 19) S K, N F K, V P K, G P K, R G T. 2012. research article effect of flavanoid rich fraction of citrus medica linn . on ethylene glycol induced urolithiasis in rats, 2(4): 109–116.
- 20) Shi Y, Wang C, Liu L, Liu Y, Wang X, Hong Y, Li Z. 2012. Antihyperuricemic and nephroprotective effects of resveratrol and its analogues in hyperuricemic mice, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mnfr.201100828>
- 21) Singh J A, Cleveland J D. 2018. Gout and the risk of myocardial infarction in older adults: A study of Medicare recipients. *Arthritis Research and Therapy*, 20(1): 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13075-018-1606-z>
- 22) Thompson P D, Panza G, Zaleski A, Taylor B. 2016. Statin-associated side effects. *Journal of the American College of Cardiology*, 67(20): 2395–2410. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jacc.2016.02.071>
- 23) Tian S, Liu Y, Feng A, Zhang S. 2020. Sex-Specific Differences in the Association of Metabolically Healthy Obesity With Hyperuricemia and a Network Perspective in Analyzing Factors Related to Hyperuricemia. *Frontiers in Endocrinology*, 11(10): 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fendo.2020.573452>
- 24) Tragni E, Catapano A L. 2012. Adherence to lipid-lowering treatment : the patient perspective, 805–814.
- 25) Venkateshan S, Subramaniyan V, Chinnasamy V, Chandiran S. 2016. Anti-oxidant and anti-hyperlipidemic activity of *Hemidesmus indicus* in rats fed with high-fat diet. *Avicenna Journal of Phytomedicine*, 6(5): 516–525. Retrieved from <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/27761421> <http://www.pubmedcentral.nih.gov/articlerender.fcgi?artid=PMC5052414>
- 26) Vinson J A, Hu S, Jung S, Stanski A M. 1998. A Citrus Extract plus Ascorbic Acid Decreases Lipids , Lipid Peroxides , Lipoprotein Oxidative Susceptibility , and Atherosclerosis in Hypercholesterolemic Hamsters, 8561(97): 1453–1459.
- 27) Walker J M, Gautier J C. 2011. *Drug Safety Evaluation - Methods and Protocols*. *Life Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4939-7172-5>
- 28) Wang C P, Wang Y, Wang X, Zhang X, Ye J F, Hu L S, Kong L D. 2011. Mulberroside A possesses potent uricosuric and nephroprotective effects in hyperuricemic mice. *Planta Medica*, 77(8): 786–794. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0030-1250599>
- 29) Ward N C, Watts G F, Eckel R H. 2019. Mechanistic Insights and Clinical Implications, 328–350. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCRESAHA.118.312782>
- 30) Whalley C V D E, Rankin S M, Hoult J R S, Jessup W, Leakeb D S. 1990. Flavonoids inhibit the oxidative modification of low density lipoproteins by macrophages, 39(11): 1743–1750.
- 31) Yang X, Yang L, Zheng H. 2010. Hypolipidemic and antioxidant effects of mulberry (*Morus alba* L.) fruit in hyperlipidaemia rats. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, 48(8–9): 2374–2379. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2010.05.074>
- 32) Zafar M S, Muhammad F, Javed I, Akhtar M, Khaliq T, Aslam B, Zafar H. 2013. White mulberry (*Morus alba*): A brief phytochemical and pharmacological evaluations account. *International Journal of Agriculture and Biology*, 15(3): 612–620.
- 33) Zhang H, Ma Z F. Effects of Mulberry Fruit (*Morus alba* L.) Consumption on Health Outcomes : A Mini-Review, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox7050069>